

International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Health Care

Available online on <http://www.rspublication.com/ijphc/index.html>
ISSN 2249 – 5738

ARTICLE INFO

©2026 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJPHC-
6A0AD09C50369

Published: 2026-05-19

DOI:
<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20286784>

Page No: 10/1-10/12

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Cite This Paper: Shigeru Suna, Masaaki Tokuda and Fumihiko Jitsunari (2026). "Effects of free radical scavenger intake on di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP) toxicity in rats". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCE AND HEALTH CARE (IJPHC)*, vol. 16, Issue 3, 2026, pp. 10/1-10/12. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20286784>

Research Article

Effects of free radical scavenger intake on di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP) toxicity in rats

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Abstract

Background: Mono(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (MEHP), a metabolite of di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP), stimulates peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors, disrupting carbohydrate and lipid metabolism. The resulting oxidative stress may be closely related to DEHP toxicity. The authors report on the toxic effects of dietary DEHP combined with drinking water containing dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), D-glucose, or D-allulose, known hydroxyl radical scavengers.

Method: Four-week-old male SD rats were divided into control, DEHP, DEHP/DMSO, DEHP/D-glucose and DEHP/D-allulose groups (6 rats per group). The treatment groups were fed 1% (w/w) DEHP diet and tap water or 0.5% (w/w) DMSO, 1% (w/w) D-glucose, or 1% (w/w) D-allulose-containing water for 1 week.

Result: DEHP intake resulted in a slight decrease in body weight gain, a significant decrease in testicular weight, and a significant increase in liver weight. A significant negative correlation was observed between plasma MEHP concentration and final rat body weight, but no effect was observed from free radical scavenger administration. D-allulose significantly improved the reduction in testicular weight, while DMSO and D-glucose slightly improved it. Relative testicular

weight (as a percentage of body weight) in the control group and the DEHP group showed a strong negative correlation with plasma or testicular MEHP concentration. In contrast, relative testicular weight in the control group and the free radical scavenger group showed a weak negative correlation with plasma or testicular MEHP concentration, and the slope of the regression line was gentler than that of the control group and the DEHP group. Testicular MEHP concentrations were skewed towards lower concentrations in the D-glucose group and D-allulose group, suggesting that D-glucose and D-allulose protect the blood-testis barrier. In addition, free radical scavengers slightly but not significantly suppressed the increase in liver weight. Plasma glucose concentrations were significantly lower in the DEHP group than in the control group, but were slightly improved by free radical scavengers. Plasma lipid-related markers such as total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and triglycerides were lower in all DEHP-treated groups than in the control group and were not improved by free radical scavengers.

Conclusion: DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose were found to improve DEHP-induced testicular atrophy and blood glucose suppression. This effect is thought to be due to the oxidant scavenging ability of DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose.

Keywords: DMSO, D-Glucose and D-Allulose; free radical scavenger, oxidative stress, DEHP, testicular atrophy, blood glucose suppression

1. Introduction

Oral exposure to di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP) results in lipase hydrolysis in the gastrointestinal tract [1, 2], producing mono(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (MEHP). MEHP stimulates peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors, disrupting carbohydrate and lipid metabolism and generating oxidative stress [3-9]. This may be closely related to the toxicity of DEHP [10-21]. The authors report on the toxic effects of dietary DEHP combined with drinking water containing dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), D-glucose, or D-allulose, known hydroxyl radical scavengers [22-24].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Animal Diet

DEHP, DMSO and D-glucose with a chemical purity of 97% or higher were purchased from Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. (Osaka). D-allulose (98% or higher purity) were provided by the Kagawa University Rare Sugar Research Center. CE-2 diets (Clea, Tokyo, Japan) containing DEHP by 1 w/w% were prepared by Oriental Yeast Company (Chiba, Japan). MEHP was purchased from Tokyo Kasei Kogyo Co., Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan). All other chemicals were the highest grade from commercial sources.

2.2. Animals and Ethics

Male Sprague-Dawley rats aged three-week-old purchased from Charles River (Kanagawa, Japan) were housed at the Laboratory Animal Center of Kagawa University. They were acclimated at 22–24 °C and 50–60% relative humidity with a 12-h light/dark cycle. The experiment protocols had the approval by the Kagawa University Animal Committee.

2.3. Experimental Design

Four-week-old rats weighing 100.0-88.0 were divided into control and treatment groups (6 rats per group). The treatment group received 1% (w / w) DEHP feed and tap water, or 1% (w / w) water with DMSO, 1% (w / w) water with D-glucose or 1% (w / w) water with D-allulose for 1 week. At the end of the experiment, rats were sacrificed under ether anesthesia. Organs were removed and weighed. Organs were frozen at -40°C until MEHP analysis. Blood samples from the heart were collected in heparinized tubes, and plasma was separated from whole blood by centrifugation at 1500 g and frozen at -40°C until MEHP and biochemical parameters were determined.

2.4. Plasma and Testicular MEHP Analysis

The MEHP levels in organs and plasma were determined by high performance liquid chromatography [25].

2.5. Plasma Biochemical Parameter Measurements

Plasma levels of glucose, total cholesterol, high density lipoprotein cholesterol and triglyceride were measured using an automated biochemical analyzer, Hitachi 7600 (Hitachi, Japan).

2.6. Statistical Analysis

Results were expressed as means \pm standard deviations (SD). Statistical analysis was performed by one-way ANOVA test followed by Dunnett's postanalysis test for multiple comparisons. $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant.

3. Results

Table 1 shows body weight gain, and Table 2 shows plasma and testicular MEHP concentrations for each treatment group; the DEHP treatment group gained less weight than the control group. As shown in Figure 1, a significant negative correlation was observed between plasma MEHP concentration and final rat body weight, but no effect was observed from free radical scavenger administration. As shown in Table 3, the DEHP treatment group had a significant decrease in testicular weight as compared to the control group, while the DEHP diet and drinking water containing DMSO and D-glucose slightly but D-allulose significantly suppressed the decrease in testicular weight. As shown in Figure 2, 3, relative testicular weight (as a percentage of body weight) in the control group and the DEHP group showed a strong negative correlation with plasma or testicular MEHP concentration. In contrast, relative testicular weight in the control group and the free radical scavenger group showed a weak negative correlation with plasma or testicular MEHP concentration, and the slope of the regression line was gentler than that of the control group and the DEHP group. Testicular MEHP concentrations were skewed towards lower concentrations (Figure 3) in the D-glucose group and D-allulose group. And a strong positive correlation was observed between plasma MEHP concentration and testicular MEHP concentration in each treatment group, but the slopes of the regression lines for the DEHP/D-glucose group and the DEHP/D-allulose group were remarkably low (Figure 4). These results suggest that D-glucose and D-allulose protect the blood-testis barrier.

Table 1. Initial and final body weights. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ as compared to control. # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$, ### $p < 0.001$ as compared to DEHP group.

Group	n	Initial body weight (g)		Final body weight (g)		
		mean	SD	mean	SD	
Control	6	93.0	3.6	148.3	4.6	#
DEHP	6	92.0	3.7	139.7	5.2	*
DEHP/DMSO	6	94.0	3.5	136.7	7.7	**
DEHP/Glucose	6	94.0	4.8	136.2	5.9	**
DEHP/Allulose	6	91.7	2.0	134.7	3.9	**

Table 2. Plasma and testicular MEHP concentrations. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 as compared to control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to DEHP group.

Group	n	Plasma MEHP (µg/ml)			Testicular MEHP (µg/g)		
		mean	SD		mean	SD	
Control	6	0.1<		###	0.1<		##
DEHP	6	42.2	10.8	***	3.6	1.5	**
DEHP/DMSO	6	41.6	8.7	***	3.4	1.2	**
DEHP/Glucose	6	39.8	9.9	***	2.0	0.4	**
DEHP/Allulose	6	50.2	22.7	***	1.9	0.5	**

Figure 1. Relationship between final body weight and plasma MEHP concentration

Table 3. Testicular weights. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 as compared to control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to DEHP group.

Group	n	Testes (g)			Relative testicular weight (%)		
		mean	SD		mean	SD	
Control	6	1.31	0.11	##	0.88	0.06	##
DEHP	6	0.77	0.11	**	0.55	0.08	**
DEHP/DMSO	6	0.97	0.25	*	0.72	0.19	
DEHP/Glucose	6	1.02	0.24		0.75	0.15	
DEHP/Allulose	6	1.06	0.27		0.78	0.18	#

Figure 2. Relationship between relative testicular weight and plasma MEHP concentration

Figure 3. Relationship between relative testicular weight and testicular MEHP concentration

Figure 4. Relationship between plasma MEHP and testicular MEHP concentration.

As shown in Table 4, the DEHP treatment group had a significant increase in liver weight as compared to the control group, while the DEHP diet and drinking water containing DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose slightly, but not significantly suppressed the increase in liver weight. Plasma glucose concentrations were significantly lower in the DEHP group than in the control group, but were slightly improved by free radical scavengers. Plasma lipid-related markers such as total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and triglycerides were lower in all DEHP-treated groups than in the control group and were not improved by free radical scavengers (Table 5, 6).

Table 4. Liver weights. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 as compared to control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to 1%DEHP group.

Group	n	Liver (g)			Relative liver weight (%)		
		mean	SD		mean	SD	
Control	6	7.03	0.35	###	4.74	0.20	###
DEHP	6	11.84	0.94	***	8.47	0.60	***
DEHP/DMSO	6	10.11	0.81	***	7.40	0.27	***
DEHP/Glucose	6	10.32	0.51	**	7.59	0.47	***
DEHP/Allulose	6	10.22	0.38	**	7.59	0.20	***

Table 5. Plasma glucose and triglyceride. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 as compared to control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to 1%DEHP group.

Group	n	Glucose (mg/dL)			Triglyceride (mg/dL)		
		mean	SD		mean	SD	
Control	6	268.5	38.7	###	48.2	24.2	##
DEHP	6	178.2	25.9	***	22.5	5.4	**
DEHP/DMSO	6	187.8	21.7	***	19.7	8.7	**
DEHP/Glucose	6	185.0	15.8	***	19.7	4.3	**
DEHP/Allulose	6	197.2	21.4	***	22.7	4.5	**

Table 6. Plasma total-cholesterol and HDL-cholesterol. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 as compared to control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to 1%DEHP group.

Group	n	Total-cholesterol (mg/dL)			HDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)		
		mean	SD		mean	SD	
Control	6	87.2	14.5	##	35.3	5.3	##
DEHP	6	68.2	3.4	**	27.8	1.9	**
DEHP/DMSO	6	71.3	7.8	*	27.3	3.7	**
DEHP/Glucose	6	65.8	5.2	**	24.5	2.2	***
DEHP/Allulose	6	71.8	10.0	*	27.3	3.5	**

4. Discussion

DEHP intake slightly reduced weight gain, significantly reduced testicular weight, and significantly increased liver weight. The weight suppression and testicular atrophy observed in this experiment were MEHP-dependent and may be a result of oxidative stress generated by MEHP. MEHP-induced oxidative stress can damage thyroid tissue and reduce thyroid hormones, which play a crucial role in the process of skeletal muscle formation [26-29]. Weight loss is thought to be due to MEHP-induced thyroid dysfunction. However, simultaneous administration of hydroxyl radical scavengers DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose improved testicular atrophy but not weight suppression. This suggests that weight suppression is not due to MEHP-induced hydroxyl radicals. D-allulose significantly improved the reduction in testicular weight,

while DMSO and D-glucose showed only slight improvement. Testicular MEHP concentrations were skewed towards lower concentrations in the D-glucose and D-allulose groups, suggesting that D-glucose and D-allulose protect the blood-testis barrier. DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose slightly, but not significantly suppressed the increase in liver weight. This may indicate the anti-inflammatory effects of free radical scavengers. Plasma glucose, total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and triglycerides were significantly lower in the DEHP-exposed group compared to the control group, although DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose administration only slightly improved plasma glucose. MEHP-induced PPAR- γ promotes lipid metabolism, and the reactive oxygen species produced may promote insulin secretion [30-33]. DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose, as hydroxyl radical scavengers, may regulate excessive insulin secretion and prevent tissue damage from oxidative stress [34, 35].

5. Conclusion

Free radical scavengers, DMSO, D-glucose and D- allulose were found to improve testicular atrophy and blood glucose suppression caused by DEHP. This effect may be due to the oxidant scavenging ability of DMSO, D-glucose, and D-allulose.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author appreciates the help of colleagues in the Kagawa University.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this work.

Statement of ethical approval

The experiment protocols had the approval by the Kagawa University Animal Committee.

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